

Trinuclear Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Manganese(II) Complexes with 1,4-Diamino-2,3-diphenyl-1,4-diaza-1,3-butadiene

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A series of trinuclear complexes of the type $M_3L_2X_6 \cdot nH_2O$ (where $M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}$ and Mn^{II} ; $L = 1,4$ -diamino-2,3-diphenyl-1,4-diaza-1,3-butadiene derived from the *in situ* reaction of benzil and hydrazine hydrate; $X = Cl^-, NO_3^-, ClO_4^-$) have been isolated and characterised. They are non-electrolytes and are paramagnetic. An approximately octahedral environment around the metal center has been proposed.

Various constituted polydentate ligands can coordinate to two or more metal ions¹. Compounds containing vicinal dihydrazones are such systems which have received considerable attention in the recent years^{2,3}. This is because of the fact that these complexes exhibit interesting chemical and spectral properties due to the presence of conjugated π -electron system $-N=C-N=C-N$ in the ligand framework and the free amino groups of the coordinated dihydrazones are ideally oriented for reaction with carbonyl groups in the presence of metal ions to give five- or six-membered annulated homo/hetero metal complexes. Very little is known about such complex compounds. With a view to isolate new homo- and hetero-polynuclear complexes, we have undertaken a study on the metal complexes of such ligands. The present communication pertains to the preparation and characterisation of a series of homo-trinuclear nickel(II), cobalt(II) and manganese(II) complexes of a dihydrazone system derived from benzil and hydrazine hydrate. Synthesis of the Schiff bases of these metallo-ligands formed by the reaction of carbonyl compounds such as acetylacetone, salicylaldehyde etc. are under investigation and the results will be communicated later.

Results and Discussion

Following an identical method for the preparation of 2,3-butanedione dihydrazone complexes, we had attempted to isolate a similar series of complexes from the reaction product of benzil and hydrazine hydrate through template method. Unlike biacetyl dihydrazone⁴, which forms complexes of the type MLX_2 , ML_2X_2 and ML_3X_2 , we isolated a completely different series of homo-trinuclear metal complexes of the type $M_3L_2X_6 \cdot nH_2O$, where $M = Ni^{II}, Co^{II}$ and Mn^{II} ; $L = 1,4$ -diamino-2,3-diphenyl-1,4-diaza-1,3-butadiene; $X = Cl^-, NO_3^-$ and ClO_4^- . The yield is almost quantitative.

In case of the copper(II) complexes, a compound of unidentified stoichiometry was isolated. All the

complexes are highly stable under normal condition. They do not have sharp melting point but decompose above 200°. The complexes are attacked by acids and alkalis. They are sparingly soluble in non-polar solvents but are highly soluble in DMF and DMSO.

Ir spectra: The ir spectra of all the complexes exhibit an identical pattern. Though they are complicated, attempts have been made to identify bands which furnish vital information regarding mode of co-ordination of the ligand moiety with the metal ion. Since the complexes were prepared *in situ*, their spectra was compared with the spectra of the complexes having similar ligand moiety⁴. The configuration of the ligand 1,4-diamino-2,3-diphenyl-1,4-diaza-1,3-butadiene undergoes drastic conformational change upon complexation. Thus the behaviour of NH_2 and $C=N$ stretching vibration will undergo drastic change. A broad band of medium intensity centered at $\sim 3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ was assigned to the combined asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of NH_2 and H_2O respectively. These bands are located at a lower frequency than usually associated with ν_{NH_2} vibration. They are even lower than the corresponding vibrations of 1,2-diphenyl-1,2-dione dihydrazone and biacetyl dihydrazone⁶ respectively. The lowering of the ν_{NH_2} is probably due to the presence of high degree of conjugation in the ligand moiety in addition to the participation of the NH_2 group in complexation. The lone-pair of electrons of nitrogen simultaneously participate in complexation and with π -electron system of the conjugated $-N=C-C=N-$, there by decreasing the $N-H$ bond strength. The water molecules seem to be coordinated as they broaden the band at $\sim 3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to intramolecular hydrogen bonding.

Probably during the *in situ* complex formation, hydrazine hydrate reacted with benzil to give 1,4-diamino-2,3-diphenyl-1,4-diaza-1,3-butadiene, which is supposed to exist in *trans*-configuration.

Since metal ions are present in the solution, they bring the dihydrazone system into *cis*-configuration with the formation of a chelate ring around the metal center. As a result, the symmetry is lowered and increases the intensity of the C=N band. In a *trans*-structure greater delocalisation occurs whereas in *cis*-form charge density is increased along C=N bond which leads to an increase in stretching frequency. The band $\sim 1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ observed in the metal chelates is due to the change in symmetry of the ligand molecule and coordination of the ligand molecule to the metal ion through the lone-pair of electrons on the azomethine nitrogen. Also there is greater width of the C=N band in the metal complexes indicating the overlap of NH_2 deformation and $-\text{C}=\text{C}$ -phenyl group vibrations on high and low frequency sides respectively.

The bands at ~ 1045 (strong intensity) and $\sim 1290\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the nickel(nitrate) complex are assigned to ν_1 and ν_2 mode of vibrations of NO_3 group respectively. The third band ν_3 expected to appear in the region $1480-1530\text{ cm}^{-1}$ could not be observed probably due to the overlap of phenyl ring vibrations. These spectral characteristics correspond to coordinated (mono- or bidentate) nitrate group⁶.

In case of the perchlorate complex, two weak bands at ~ 1140 and 1020 cm^{-1} and a strong band at $\sim 910\text{ cm}^{-1}$ were observed. These bands are characteristics of unidentate (coordinated) ClO_4^- group⁷. The former two bands have been assigned to ν_3 and the latter to ν_4 mode of vibrations of a coordinated ClO_4^- group. Thus it can be concluded that NO_3^- and ClO_4^- groups are coordinated in an unidentate manner, a fact further supported by the low molar conductance values.

Electronic spectra and magnetic properties: The nickel(II) complexes are of spin-free type and show magnetic moment in the range 2.93–3.11 B.M. at room temperature. These values are in good agreement with those complexes with $^3A_{2g}$ or $^3B_{1g}$ ground term. They show three distinct bands which clearly approach the spectral features of known octahedral complexes⁸. A weak and broad band centered $\sim 12200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and two intense bands at ~ 18180 and 26500 cm^{-1} are assigned under octahedral micro-symmetry to $^3A_{2g} \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}$, $^3A_{2g} \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}(F)$ and $^3A_{2g} \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}(P)$ transition respectively. The latter band is more intense presumably due to the overlap of the charge transfer band. The width of the first band manifests distortion probably along the trigonal axis.

The cobalt(II) complexes are paramagnetic with their magnetic moment values lying in the range 3.89–4.62 B.M. All these complexes exhibit ligand field bands ($14500-21700\text{ cm}^{-1}$) possessing multiplet band structure assignable to $^4T_{1g} \rightarrow ^4A_{2g}$ and $^4T_{1g} \rightarrow ^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions, generally characteristic of octahedral or more appropriately tetragonal ligand field around the metal ion⁹.

Bands around 18000 , 25000 and 28300 cm^{-1} in the electronic spectrum of the manganese(II) complex are assigned to $^6A_{1g}(S) \rightarrow ^4T_{1g}(S)$, $^6A_{1g}(S) \rightarrow ^4E_g + ^4A_{1g}(G)$ and $^6A_{1g}(S) \rightarrow ^4T_{2g}(D)$ multiplicity forbidden transitions respectively. The band intensities and their position in addition to the room temperature magnetic moment values (5.32 B.M.) suggest an octahedral field around the metal ion¹⁰.

Thermal analyses: Since their ir spectra of the complexes indicate the presence of water molecules, thermal analyses were undertaken to ascertain their nature. All the complexes follow an identical pattern of thermal decomposition. In case of the nitrate complex of nickel(II) there was no mass-loss upto 150° suggesting the absence of lattice water. The first weight-loss was encountered at $\sim 180^\circ$ corresponding to the loss of four water molecules. The existence of an exothermic peak in the DTA curve at the same temperature suggest that they are all in the same chemical environment¹¹. Based on this observation and ir spectral data we are of the opinion that the water molecules are coordinated to the two side metal ions where as the central metal ion satisfy its 5th and 6th coordination number by anions.

A stable product continues upto 355° after which the organic constituents of the complexes start decomposing, finally leaving behind the metal oxides. The thermal stability of the complexes follow the order: $\text{Ni} > \text{Mn} > \text{Co}$.

Experimental

Benzil was prepared from benzoin (E. Merck) according to the literature method¹². Hydrazine hydrate (90%) was of B.D.H. quality. All other metal salts and solvents were either of B.D.H. or E. Merck grade. Solvents were used as such.

Hexachlorobis(1,4-diamino-2,3-diphenyl-1,4-diazabutadiene)trnickel(II): A mixture of benzil (0.2 mol) in ethanol and an alcoholic solution of $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.3 mol) was warmed to boiling for 0.5 h and the hydrazine hydrate (0.4 mol) was added to it dropwise with constant stirring and refluxed for 2 h. The resulting light grey solid was cooled, filtered, washed with alcohol and ether and dried at room temperature. The nitrate and perchlorate complexes were prepared in a similar manner.

Hexachlorobis(1,4-diamino-2,3-diphenyl-1,4-diazabutadiene)trcobalt(II): A mixture of benzil (0.2 mol) in ethanol and an alcoholic solution of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.3 mol) was warmed to boiling for 0.5 h and then hydrazine hydrate (0.4 mol) was added to it dropwise with constant stirring and refluxed on a water-bath for 2 h. The resulting pink solid after cooling was washed with alcohol and ether and dried at room temperature. The nitrate complex and manganese complexes were prepared in a similar way.

Nickel was estimated gravimetrically as nickel

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Yield %	Molecular weight Found/(Calcd.)	μ_{eff} B.M.	ΔM $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				
						Metal	N*	C	H	Cl
$\text{Ni}_3\text{L}_2\text{Cl}_6(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4$	Light grey	90	933 (937)	2.93	11.2	18.49 (18.56)	11.91 (11.95)	35.77 (35.85)	3.78 (3.84)	22.69 (22.73)
$\text{Ni}_3\text{L}_2(\text{NO}_3)_6(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4$	Pink	91	1094 (1 096)	3.11	12.8	15.81 (15.87)	17.81 (17.88)	30.59 (30.65)	3.19 (3.28)	—
$\text{Ni}_3\text{L}_2(\text{ClO}_4)_6(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4$	Yellowish green	94	1305 (1 318)	2.98	14.0	13.16 (13.20)	8.41 (8.49)	25.41 (25.49)	2.64 (2.73)	16.09 (16.16)
$\text{Co}_3\text{L}_2\text{Cl}_6(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4$	Pink	93	932 (938)	4.62	13.3	18.80 (18.86)	11.88 (11.94)	35.73 (35.82)	3.77 (3.83)	22.76 (22.70)
$\text{Co}_3\text{L}_2(\text{NO}_3)_6(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4$	Rose	91	1092 (1 097)	4.62	14.1	16.09 (16.13)	17.79 (17.86)	30.56 (30.62)	3.22 (3.28)	—
$\text{Mn}_3\text{L}_2\text{Cl}_6(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4$	White	92	924 (926)	5.32	15.6	17.78 (17.81)	12.01 (12.09)	36.21 (36.28)	3.81 (3.88)	22.91 (23.03)

* Including nitrate nitrogen.

dimethylglyoxime and cobalt volumetrically. C, H and N were estimated using a MLW-CHN micro-analyser. Magnetic susceptibility was measured with a Gouy balance at room temperature using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{CNS})_4]$ as calibrant. Molecular weight was determined by Rast's method. The analytical and physical data of the complexes are recorded in Table 1.

Infrared ($400-4000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and reflectance spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 983 and Cary 2390 spectrophotometers in KBr and MgCO_3 pellets respectively. The molar conductivity of the complexes in DMF was measured with a Toshniwal conductivity bridge.

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References

1. J. CHAKRAVARTY and B. SAHOO, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, 20, 431.

- B. K. MOHAPATRA and B. SAHOO, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, 21, 376.
- J. CHAKRAVARTY and B. SAHOO, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, 19, 441.
- H. C. RAI and B. SAHOO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 52, 646; J. CHAKRAVARTY and B. SAHOO, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, 19, 442.
- R. C. STOUFER and D. H. BUSCH, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 82, 3491.
- P. W. BALL and A. B. BLAKES, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1969, 1415.
- A. E. WICKENDEN and R. A. KRAUSE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 4, 404.
- D. M. L. GOODGAME, M. GOODGAME, M. A. HITCHMAN and J. M. WEEKS, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1966, 1769; D. A. ROWLEY and R. S. DRAGO, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, 7, 795; A. B. P. LEVER, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1968, 3, 119.
- L. SACCONI, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1970, 248; J. FERGUSON, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, 12, 249; M. CIAMPOLINE, *Struct. Bonding*, 1969, 6, 52.
- C. J. BALLHAUSEN, "Introduction to Ligand Field Theory", McGraw Hill, New York, 1962, p. 245; V. BANERJI and A. K. DEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, 59, 991.
- S. K. SRIVASTAVA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1979, 17, 193; P. L. MAURYA, B. V. AGARWAL and A. K. DEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, 59, 29.
- A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", 3rd ed., ELBS, London, p. 714.